

GDPR Notice

Purposes

The information collected through this form is recorded in a computerized file by the French Association of Economic Sciences (AFSE) for the AFSE committee responsible for promoting the role of women in economics: AFSE-WinE (Women in Economics). The purpose is to evaluate the mentorship program launched in 2024.

Legal Basis for Processing

Regulation (EU) 2016/679 – Article 6(a): "The data subject has given consent to the processing of their personal data for one or more specific purposes."

The legal basis for processing is consent (in accordance with Article 7 of the GDPR).

Recipients

The data collected through this form will remain anonymous and will be shared only with the following recipients within the French Association of Economic Sciences:

- Members of the WinE committee

Categories of Data Processed

- Professional status
- Family responsibilities
- Location (France or abroad)
- Research topic
- Evaluation of the mentorship program (Women/Men).

Retention

The data will be retained for 10 years.

Your Rights

You have the right to access, correct, delete, or restrict the processing of your data.

The data controller is the French Association of Economic Sciences (AFSE).

Your personal data is stored on servers located within the European Union, either internally on our secure servers or externally by a duly selected provider. As the data controller, we implement necessary security and confidentiality procedures to prevent any risk of fraudulent access, theft, deterioration, or accidental loss of your data.

You have the right to access, correct, delete your personal data, and oppose its processing.

Visit the website cnil.fr for more information about your rights.

To exercise these rights or for any questions about the processing of your data within this framework, you can contact the Data Protection Officer at the following address:

dpo@groupe-genes.fr

Or by postal mail:

French Association of Economic Sciences (AFSE)

AFSE Secretariat c/o LEDA-DIAL Secretariat

Université Paris Dauphine

Place du Maréchal de Lattre de Tassigny

75116 PARIS

If you believe, after contacting us, that your "Information and Freedoms" rights are not being respected, you can file a complaint with the CNIL.